

MODERN METHODS IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the methodology of foreign language teaching, the history of its development as a science, the types of modern methods used in foreign language teaching methods and their use.

Keywords: methodology, innovation, foreign language, communication, skills, competencies, didactics, intercultural communication.

Language learning is one of the most important areas in human society. Language, which is a means of communication, in the natural environment, that is, in the family, among the public or can be acquired in an organized manner. Knowledge of language phenomena is taught theoretically. Languages in our time when international relations are on the rise knowledge, especially multilingualism, is of great importance. Study in our country students usually study three languages. These languages are special are managed by names. These are: mother tongue, second language, and foreign language. Mother tongue It is the first language that plays a special role in the formation of thinking. Second when talking about language, it means brothers and sisters of other nationalities, it is considered as the language of neighbors.

The main concepts of methodology - method, method, principle. Didactics – what shall we teach? is the content of teaching. Methodology - how do we teach? Education means methods and methods. Method - the concept of methodology is Greek-Latin "methodos" is derived from the word "methodus" and means ways leading to a certain

goal, means method. Narrow and broad meaning of the term in different literature can be found. The term "methodology" in a narrow sense is a concrete lesson of education means the concept related to the process. Lesson planning and training covering instructions related to the preparation of materials interpreted as a controlled learning process.

The method of teaching a foreign language is a practical method of teaching a foreign language. Ensuring the achievement of general educational, educational and developmental goals the complex of teacher and student activities is understood. The term method is "teaching it is used in the meanings of "sum of methods" and "direction of education". The first In the theory of education, if the process is used in the sense of methods, it is used in the second sense we can find it in works on the history of teaching methodology. For example, a foreign language translation method of teaching, correct method, conscious-comparative method, traditional method, intensive method and others.

Method without translation. Various forms of this method are known historically. They can be divided into two large groups: natural and correct methods. In a natural way learning a foreign language should be similar to the conditions of mastering the mother tongue. Method the main goal is to learn to read and write by learning to speak a foreign language the idea that it will be possible to get is formed in the form of a practical goal. Natural the most important of the principles included in the method is to create a language environment. Go ahead there are different approaches to the application of applied methodical principles was. This can be clearly seen in the creative activity of the method exponents.

In the methodology of foreign language teaching, the expression of intercultural communication is widespread is being used. It is this concept that we use in different contexts we can use. Actually: Intercultural communication - different culture social origin, mentality, national character, lifestyle, traditions of its representatives, communication-information about the system of values and others.

In this process, students are introduced to the culture of the country being studied respect, patience and proper understanding of the culture of another country it is necessary to educate and develop in the spirit. Pedagogical communication is the interaction between the teacher and the student cooperation, it is mutual information exchange, first of all educational information is based on the understanding of the pedagogical communication partner, as well as mutual cooperation helps to carry out activities. Information is also verbal, that is, speech through non-verbal means. In the process of pedagogical communication the teacher should play the main role and be an example for students. This evaluated by his communicative culture.

Learning a foreign language is a multifaceted teaching, and a person is complicated in this process experiences psychological changes. Including mother tongue and foreign language a comparison process occurs. Different methods of teaching in this process of technologies are used. With the help of modern pedagogical technologies teaching by comparing a foreign language with the mother tongue gives an effective result. Foreign language teaching requires knowledge of its methodology. Methodology and technologies are important in the process of learning a foreign language. The lesson There are different methods of methodological science in organization. Foreign language teaching widely used methods in the methodology: communicative didactic method, a method of organizing intercultural communication and a method of organizing an exercise is considered All three methods are closely related and complement each other.

The teacher's communicative culture is his educational process professional-pedagogical communication with subjects. Communicative culture as a necessary level, it can be defined that the teacher has his own can positively accept students and colleagues, and education and upbringing can ensure the achievement of its goals. Communicative culture its social significance is that the teacher who holds it is the whole educational process can create a positive psychological climate in the interaction of its subjects, education important principles of modernization being - implements humanism and democratization. Personal the importance is for the pedagogue who has

a communicative culture his confidence is high, he enjoys communication with his pupil, he feels free in the chosen work activity. Not only for successful activity of the teacher-teacher subject, pedagogical and psychological knowledge, as well as another special feature -communication skills and competences are definitely necessary.

Studying a foreign language is related to the science of methodology and the science of didactics is based on communicativeness and communicative didactic method occurs. In the process of applying the method of communicative didactics, the pedagogue the method of formation of intercultural communication is also formed. Learning a foreign language as a result, the culture of another country is also assimilated. It is necessary in foreign language education "training organization technology" is important for acquiring knowledge earns.

Practice is the best way to master all knowledge. Exercise is not only in foreign language education, but also in mastering knowledge of all fields gives a positive result. Effective organization of the lesson, the activity of the pedagogue in it and the role of modern pedagogical technologies is incomparable. Learning a foreign language organization of the process with a communicative approach, the next stage to reach the level of intercultural communication, and to achieve such results, It is important to pay attention to the last step, "exercise technology". Modern pedagogical information for effective organization of the foreign language teaching process it is necessary to acquire knowledge of communication technologies.

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